

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PALEOLITHIC WORKSHOP IN JIZZAKH REGION

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Abstract. *Stone Age monuments are rare on the territory of Jizzakh. For the first time in the 80s of the 20th century, L. Sverchkov found a pencil-shaped core belonging to the Neolithic era in Peshagorsoy, Zomin district, Jizzakh region, and later in 2000, specialists from the Archaeological Institute of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan managed to find a stone core dating back to the Paleolithic period, in the area of the village of Chimqorgon, Forish district. In 2012, members of Jizzakh detachment of the Archaeological Institute of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan conducted field research in Forish district. Such locations as Yangikishok, Azimbulak, Gordara, Chashmai-Doston were also discovered. The findings listed above were a drawback, and our conclusions about the Stone Age of Jizzakh did not reach a clear conclusion. But in the summer of 2023, scientists from Samarkand Archaeological Institute named after Y. Gulyamova conducted field exploration work in Gallaaral and Forish districts of Jizzakh region. As a result, they discovered a Paleolithic workshop in the village of Ugat, Gallaorol district, and the village of Narvon, Forish district. This article is devoted to the study of some considerations about the Ogat Paleolithic workshop.*

Keywords: *nucleus, Farish region, paleolithic, flake, sandstone, dorsal, ventral, distal, impact platform.*

Introduction

The study of the ancient Stone Age of Jizzakh region, which is adjacent to Samarkand oasis, has long been one of the neglected areas in the research of the Republic's Paleolithic scholars. Initially, in 1986, L. Sverchkov conducted research in Jizzakh region and, as a result, managed to discover a chisel-like nucleus dating to the Neolithic period in Zomin district, Peshagorsoy. Later, research carried out by the Paleolithic group of the Archaeology Institute of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan resulted in the identification of several Paleolithic sites in Jizzakh region. The first Paleolithic stone tool from Jizzakh region was found in 2000 in the sand dunes of Chimqorgon village area in Forish district [Pardayev, Sayfullayev, 2000; Sayfullayev, 2003, p. 74]. This finding, a nucleus worked from quartzite, was found to be similar in technique and raw materials to the materials from Qotirbulok site. This discovery, firstly, indicates that Jizzakh region was also inhabited by Paleolithic humans, and secondly, it shows that their material culture had similarities with the cultures of the early tribal societies of Samarkand oasis.

In the spring of 2012, a group of young researchers from the Archaeology Institute of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, part of Jizzakh team, conducted search work in the western foothills of Yuqori Uchma village in Forish district of Jizzakh region. As a result, new sites were identified, including Yangiqishloq, Azimbuloq, Gur Dara, and Chashmai-Doston [Sayfullayev, Ergashov et al., 2012, p. 189]. In the summer of 2023, scientists from Samarkand Archaeological Institute named after Y. Gulomov, under the Cultural Heritage Agency, conducted field research in the Gallaorol and Forish districts of Jizzakh region. As a result, Paleolithic stone tools were discovered in Ugat village of Gallaorol district and in Narvon village of Forish district.

It is known to us that many stone workshops are located in Uzbekistan, and extensive research has been conducted in these workshops (Uchtut, Qopchigoy, Okhangaron, Qizilqir, Kukayoz 1-8, Sulton Uvaystog (23-24 sites), Kukcha, Qoraquduq). These stone processing workshops have been divided into two types: site-workshops and true workshops. In turn, the site-workshops are further divided into two groups: the first group includes the sites located directly near stone mines. The activity of the population in such workshops was mainly related to collecting raw materials and performing primary and secondary processing of stones. The second group of site-workshops is distinguished by the fact that they are located far from the raw material mines. The population of these workshops brought the raw materials from outside and processed them fully at the site. A characteristic feature of both groups of site-workshops is the presence of household items, which testify to the seasonal or permanent habitation of these sites, along with stones that have undergone primary processing.

True workshops are characterized solely by the presence of items related to the production of stone tools. These sites do not show signs of long-term human habitation. Such workshops are typically located near specific stone deposits that are suitable for making tools. These workshops are further divided into two types based on the nature of human production activity: the first type of true workshops is that where primary processing of stones takes place and rough tools are flaked from them. In these areas, the raw materials were obtained by simple open methods during the Paleolithic and Neolithic periods. From the Neolithic period onward, raw materials began to be obtained by digging pits, wells, and mines.

The second type of true workshops, in contrast to the first, not only involved primary processing of stones but also the production of specialized types of tools. During the Paleolithic period, it is doubtful that site workshops were "home" workshops or "specialized" workshops. However, V.P. Lybin added that such workshops might have existed even during the Muste period [Ergashov Odil. Samarkand 2014, p. 4-9].

The Ogat workshop is located in the northeastern part of the Ogat village, Gallaorol district, and about 200 stone tools were collected (Table 1). The stone tools are mostly primary processed, with few tooth-like tools. The collection includes chopping, cleaver, blade, core (otshep), and Levallois-type tools. The Ogat people were successful in making stone tools using local raw materials as much as possible. According to the technical-typological characteristics of the materials, it would be appropriate to consider the Ogat stone tool workshop as belonging to the late Middle Paleolithic and the beginning of the Upper Paleolithic. This is because, in addition to breaking with heavy stone hammers, some tools in the collection were also broken using organic light stone hammers. It is known that this flaking technique emerged in the Upper Paleolithic. Additionally, some stone tools show bifacial processing.

Regarding the Narvon find site, despite its scarcity, it is dated to the Middle Paleolithic, as most of the tools in the collection were broken with heavy stone hammers, and the striking area protruded due to the strong impact. Both sites, based on the processing technique and raw materials, resemble the materials from the Qutirbuloq site (Pardayev, Pardayev, Xolboyev, Xolmatov, Imomov, Tursunqulov, Ruziboyev, Qandakharov, 2023, p. 58).

The first stone tool in our collection, found in Ogat, is a large-sized core of the Combe-Capelle type, measuring 12.5x11x2.5 mm. Based on the negative scars on its dorsal side, it has a characteristic opposite longitudinal direction. The striking area is flat (Figure 1). The next tool, found in Narvon, is a large-sized core made of sandstone, measuring 11x11.7x2.7 mm. About 80%

of its dorsal surface is covered with natural cortex. Only two negative scars are present on the right lateral part of the proximal end. The striking area is natural (Figure 2).

Table 1.

<i>"2023 - Ogat Workshop: The tools collected from the surface"</i>	
Cleaver	4
Chopping tool	2
Nucleus-like fragment	5
Levallois point	1
Scraper	1
Plate	10
Blade	48
Total :	71

Picture 1: Flake (Ogat finding)

The next tool, also found in Narvon, is a core where only the medial part is preserved, while the distal and proximal parts are broken. Its size is 6.3x4.1x0.8 mm. Based on the negative scars on its dorsal side, it has a characteristic opposite longitudinal direction (Figure 3,1). The next stone tool, found in Narvon, is a core with the size of 3.8x4.7x0.6 mm. Based on the negative scars on its dorsal side, it has a characteristic opposite longitudinal direction. The striking area is bifacial (Figure 3,2).

In the Ogat Paleolithic workshop, quartzite and calcified limestone raw materials were primarily used. Although quartz raw material was also present at the site, it was not used for making tools. According to the technical-typological characteristics, the Ogat Paleolithic workshop is dated to the Middle and Upper Paleolithic.

Picture 2. Flake (Narvon finding)

Picture 3. 1-2: Flakes (Narvon finding)

Conclusion. Thus, no complex site similar to the Ogat workshop had been discovered in Jizzax region before, and the discovery of the Ogat and Narvon sites in Jizzax area is expected to become another significant archaeological finding in the history of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Pardaev M.H., Sayfullaev B.Q. "The Traces of Our Ancient Ancestors in the Jizzax Region." *Jizzax Haqiqati* Newspaper, May 2000.
2. Sayfullaev B.K. "Paleolithic of the Zarafshan River Valley and the North-Eastern Kyzylkum." Dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Historical Sciences. Samarkand, 2003.
3. Sayfullaev B.Q., Ergashev O.T., Rakhimov K.A., Rajabov A.Y., Allayorov O., Pardaev Sh.M. "The Paleolithic Period of the Jizzax Region" in *Archaeological Research in Uzbekistan*. Samarkand, 2012. – pp. 189-194.
4. Jo‘rakulova D.M. "The Study of the Paleolithic Period in Uzbekistan in the Years of Independence" // Editor-in-chief Asqarov A // Tashkent, 2019. pp. 152-157.
5. Ergashev O.T. "Stone Tool Workshops of Kokayoz Site." *Zarafshon* Publishing House, Samarkand, 2014.
6. Kasimov M.R., Krizhevskaya L.Ya. "On the Classification of Flint Tool Manufacturing Workshops." *SA*, No. 1. Moscow, 1969.
7. Pardaev M., Pardaev Sh., Xolboev Z., Xolmatov A., Imomov A., Tursunqulov F., Ro‘ziboev T., Qandaxarov I. "The New Paleolithic Workshop Found in the Jizzax Region." In the materials of the international conference *Stone Age Cultures of Central Asia at the Crossroads*. Held on November 27, 2023. Samarkand, 2023. pp. 55-62.